

Supplementary information on the article: Aridity preferences alter the relative importance of abiotic and biotic drivers on plant species abundance in global drylands

Miguel Berdugo, Fernando T. Maestre, Sonia Kéfi, Nicolas Gross, Yoann Le Bagousse-Pinguet & Santiago Soliveres

Supporting information:

1. Figure S1
2. Figure S2
3. Figure S3
4. Figure S4
5. Appendix S1
6. Appendix S2
7. Appendix S3

Figure S1. Map showing the geographical position of the 157 sites used in this study (red points).

Figure S2. Example of aridity niches for *Stipa tenacissima* (a) and *Maireana brevifolia* (b), including the features measured on them. AI = aridity index. Photographs of each species are shown in the figure. Authors: a) Lumbar~commons wiki; b) BY-SA 3.0, downloaded from Wikipedia under creative commons license.

Figure S3. Variation in the relationship between aridity and community weighted niche optimum (a), amplitude (b) and skewness (c) when using the same number of points at both sides of the intermediate aridity level of the study (Aridity = 0.6). We performed this regression 100 times by keeping the sites with aridity lower than 0.6 (N=24) and

bootstrapping sites with aridity higher than 0.6 (so that total $N = 48$ for each regression). Each dot represents the community observed in one of the sites surveyed. The degree of transparency of the data points is inversely proportional to the number of times the point was used. The blue line is the loess smoothed trend observed in each of the 100 bootstrapped samplings. The black line in a) represents the 1:1 line and in c) the CMW (niche skewness) = 0 value indicating the point at which skewness changes direction.

Figure S4. The standardized effects sizes of facilitation, competition and aridity along an aridity gradient for specialised (CWSkewness < 0, a) and non-specialised (CWSkewness > 0, b) communities. This analysis was performed by fitting a linear mixed model throughout a moving window (see figure 1d) in two subsets of our study sites according to CWskewness. Bootstrapped coefficients of mixed models regression within the 95 % confidence intervals are shown for each step of the moving window. Lines represent the gam-smoothed trends of variation of the effect sizes.

APPENDIX S1: ADDITIONAL INFORMATION ON THE EXTRACTION OF SPECIES NICHES CURVES

Occurrence data

We downloaded species occurrences (i.e. presence data) of the 898 species found in the drylands surveyed from the Global Biodiversity Information Facility (GBIF, <http://www.gbif.org/>). GBIF offers a free and comprehensive database of different species all over the world, including their synonyms, growth form, and occurrences. Despite some limitations of GBIF data (Beck *et al.* 2013a, 2014), this database is commonly used to extract species occurrences and to build species distributions models (SDMs, see Deblauwe *et al.* 2016, Gomez & Cassini 2015, Leiblein-Wild *et al.* 2015).

We removed the occurrences that either did not lay on earth ground (i.e. data that are not properly georeferenced) or were considered outliers according to the bulk of occurrences found. For doing the latter, we calculated the centroid of all occurrences for each species, and calculated the Euclidian distance between each occurrence and the centroid. We removed those occurrences that fell out of the 95% confidence interval of the distance probability density function if two conditions were satisfied: i) they were separated by more than 500 km from the centroid, and ii) they occurred further than 500 km from the nearest conspecific. By doing this outlier identification, we avoid accounting for single occurrences far from the species distribution centroid or far from a particular distribution cluster. The threshold used here (500 km) is sufficiently rare for plants to accomplish a frequent (1 event each 10 years) and/or successful (probability of seed arrival $\approx 10^{-20}$; probability of seed survival $\approx 10^{-4}$) dispersal process, even being within the range of distances for which the probabilities of seed dispersal are impossible to estimate with current methods due to their low values (Nathan 2006).

Because the sampling effort of data from GBIF varies depending on the geographical area considered, we used a resampling method to remove points that were too close to each other (Phillips *et al.* 2009; see also Berdugo et al., 2018 for the code used to perform this task automatically). We discarded all occurrences falling within 10 arc-minutes (≈ 18.5 km) distance from another. There is no specific method in the literature to select the threshold of grid size that best avoids sampling bias effects, especially when dealing with that many species. So, we selected 10 arc-minutes as it maximizes the relationship between the curves of species remaining versus minimum number of occurrences needed to perform SDMs and the grid size (Figure SA1.1).

Extracting niches

To model the aridity niches of the species studied, we used General Additive Models (GAM, Wood 2006) with the “gam” library (Hastie 2017) in R (R Development Core Team 2008). The methods and rationale of SDMs rely on the fact that the environmental envelope depicting the points in which a species is occurring is the conditional probability of the environment given that the species occurs there (i.e., $P(\text{environ}|1)$). To extract the probability of the species occurrence given a certain environmental condition (and thus its environmental niche), the Bayesian principle might be used as follows:

$$P(1|\text{environ}) = \frac{P(\text{environ}|1) \cdot P(1)}{P(\text{environ})},$$

where $P(1)$ is the probability of the species to occur independently of the environmental condition (which is a surrogate of prevalence for that species) and $P(\text{environ})$ is the probability distribution of the environment. This equation can be scaled to the prevalence of the species, giving a species sensitivity index equivalent to assuming all species being equally prevalent (i.e., being their occurrence only dependent on the environmental conditions irrespective of whether they are rare or not), as follows:

$$\frac{P(1|environ)}{P(1)} = \frac{P(environ|1)}{P(environ)} \text{ equation S1}$$

Only $P(environ|1)$ and $P(environ)$ are required to estimate this sensitivity index.

$P(environ|1)$ can be extracted from GBIF data since it is the frequency distribution of each species occurrence according to the environmental predictor(s) chosen (aridity in our case). The estimation of $P(environ)$ is the description of a geographic envelope of the abiotic variable of interest (called background sampling and representing the environmental conditions offered to the species within the region of study). In other words, we calculated the relative performance of a species as a relativized estimation of the aridity values in which it is found respect to how abundant are these aridity values within the study region. For this, we used the ecological realms (“ecozones”) described by Pielou (1979) and Udvardy & Udvardy (1975) as environmental envelopes (<http://www.worldwildlife.org/biomes>). This is a broad, generally accepted and meaningful eco-geographical division that accounts for the evolutionary history of the plants (Udvardy & Udvardy 1975; Dixon *et al.* 2014; Elder *et al.* 2016). Therefore, we assumed that each species has an environmental envelope corresponding to the aridity values of the bioclimatic zone in which it is living. We sampled 1000 points randomly throughout each ecological realm to use them as background sampling. We used these points to extract the environmental envelope from the maps. We classified each species according to the ecological realm they occupy, and for each species added the corresponding background sampling. In the case that more than one realm was occupied, we added background sampling from as many realms as were occupied by the species, so that no more than 1000 points were introduced as background sampling anyway. The envelope entails a correction of the environmental availability for the species. For instance, it corrects for the fact that a given set of environmental conditions are infrequent in nature.

Provided the background sampling and species occurrences, GAM models were used with a family of binomial distributions. We constrained the degrees of freedom of the model

to avoid over-fitting. To do so, we implemented the models using 2 to 6 degrees of freedom for each species, and selected that scoring a lower Akaike Information Criterion (AIC) value. This metric penalizes the number of parameters used in the estimation and allowed us to keep the most parsimonious model that explained the most variance possible.

We retained only those species for which we had at least 20 occurrences ($N = 701$), as this threshold has been identified as sufficient to account for rare species in SDMs (Williams *et al.* 2009; Gogol-Prokurat 2011). We used the True Skill Satatistic (TSS, Allouche *et al.* 2006) to validate the niches fitted. This method separates 10% of the occurrences to perform a validation process of the niche. Validation is performed by predicting the probability of occurrence of the species throughout the study region based on the niche and testing whether the cases saved for validation satisfy the occurrence patterns predicted by the niche (Raes & ter Steege 2007). This statistic measures the performance of the models, being higher than 0 if the model differs from random and considered a good model if values are higher than 0.4. The values obtained are displayed in Figure SA 1.2. and are available together with the data used in this analysis (Berdugo *et al.* 2018). To see if our main results differed when including only species for which we had good models, we run the analyses described in step ii only for the species that had TSS values larger than 0.4. Our results were very similar to those reported in the original paper (see Figure SA 1.3).

Figure SA. 1.1. Number of species that would be lost versus the minimum number of occurrences required to conduct species distribution models for different thresholds of grid sampling bias. Grid sampling bias indicates the size of a grid within which occurrences of species are considered to be the same occurrence. We selected 10 arc minutes as it represents the curve that best maximizes the number of species remaining with the widest grid size.

Figure SA 1.2. Histogram of the 838 values (one per species) of True Skill Statistic for the validation of niches extracted using GAM (a), and using MAXENT with one (b) or several (c) variables.

Figure SA. 1.3. Results of the analysis described in step ii of the main manuscript with the GAM niches and $TSS > 0.4$. Standardized effect sizes of facilitation, competition and aridity-driven abundance (a) and the interactions between aridity-driven abundance and competition and facilitation (b) as drivers of species relative abundance along an aridity gradient. This analysis is performed by fitting a linear mixed models throughout a moving window in a subset of the sites surveyed following our aridity gradient. Bootstrapped coefficients of this regression with their 95% confidence intervals are shown for each step of the moving window. Lines represent the gam-smoothed trends of variation of the effect sizes.

APPENDIX S2: CONSISTENCY OF THE ANALYSIS TO NICHE

EXTRACTION PROCEDURE

Using MAXENT

Provided the background sampling and species occurrences, MAXENT uses a machine-learning procedure to estimate the response curve of niche adequacy based on equation S1 (see Elith et al. 2011 for a review). MAXENT uses different combinations of linear, product, quadratic, hinge, threshold and categorical fitting (called features) during this machine-learning procedure, and calculates the estimates of the coefficients of these different fittings. Then, MAXENT calculates the log likelihood of the different fittings and penalizes both the number of parameters and the number of features used in the fitting procedure using a method called regularization (Tibshirani 1996). MAXENT maximizes the penalized log likelihood, which is equivalent to minimize the relative entropy of the model affected by error-bound constraints, to provide the niche. To model the aridity niches of the species studied, we used MAXENT (Dudik, Philips & Shapire 2004) with the “dismo” library (Hijmans *et al.* 2015) in R (R Development Core Team 2008).

The results of validation with the TSS statistic are displayed in Figure SA 1.2, and are reported together with the data used in this analysis (Berdugo *et al.* 2018). The overall results of the manuscript remained the same when using this statistical technique instead of GAM models to calculate AAb (see Figure SA 2.1.) and even when doing this analysis only with species scoring $TSS > 0.4$ (thus considered a good model; Figure SA 2.2.).

Figure SA 2.1. Results of the analysis described in step ii of the manuscript with Aab extracted from niches calculated using MAXENT. Standardized effect sizes of facilitation, competition and aridity-driven abundance (a) and the interactions between aridity-driven abundance and competition and facilitation (b) as drivers of species relative abundance along an aridity gradient. This analysis is performed by fitting a linear mixed models throughout a moving window in a subset of the sites surveyed following our aridity gradient. Bootstrapped coefficients of this regression with their 95% confidence intervals are shown for each step of the moving window. Lines represent the gam-smoothed trends of variation of the effect sizes.

Figure SA. 2.2. Results of the moving window approach described in step ii of the manuscript with Aab calculated with MAXENT outputs for species with TSS higher than 0.4 (thus considered a good model). Standardized effect sizes of facilitation, competition and aridity-driven abundance (a) and the interactions between aridity-driven abundance and competition and facilitation (b) as drivers of species relative abundance along an aridity gradient. This analysis is performed by fitting a linear mixed models throughout a moving window in a subset of the sites surveyed following our aridity gradient. Bootstrapped coefficients of this regression with their 95% confidence intervals are shown for each step of the moving window. Lines represent the gam-smoothed trends of variation of the effect sizes.

Several abiotic predictors

Because the niches obtained with SDMs in the original method described in step i might exhibit confounding factors if more abiotic variables were included, we also conducted SDMs including other abiotic variables of interest. We selected the minimum temperature of the coldest month, elevation, sand content and precipitation seasonality in addition to aridity. Although other variables might be of interest (e.g., average temperature and soil carbon content) we chose these factors because they did not show correlation with aridity in the background data points (i.e., pearson's r lower than 0.4; see Table SA 2.1). We also discarded maximum temperature of the hottest month because it was very correlated with minimum temperature (pearson's $r > 0.7$, see Table SA. 2.1). The minimum temperature of the coldest month and precipitation seasonality were extracted from the Worldclim database (Hijmans *et al.* 2005, bioclim variables 2 and 5), sand content was extracted from the ISRIC maps database (Batjes 2012) and elevation was extracted from ASTER global digital elevation maps (ASTER GDEM).

Table SA. 2.1. Pearson's r correlation matrix between predictors used in the multi-varied SDMs. minT= minimum temperature of the coldest month; maxT= maximum temperature of the hottest month; Pptseas= seasonality of precipitation, ele= elevation; sand = sand content of the soil; carbon= carbon content of the soil. In red: variables that were discarded.

	Aridity	minT	maxT	Pptseas	ele	sand	Carbon
Aridity	1.00	-0.06	0.39	0.37	0.13	0.39	-0.41
minT	-0.06	1.00	0.73	0.23	-0.07	0.14	-0.42
maxT	0.39	0.73	1.00	0.42	-0.05	0.28	-0.54
Pptseas	0.37	0.23	0.42	1.00	0.13	0.17	-0.32
ele	0.13	-0.07	-0.05	0.13	1.00	0.09	-0.11
sand	0.39	0.14	0.28	0.17	0.09	1.00	-0.26
Carbon	-0.41	-0.42	-0.54	-0.32	-0.11	-0.26	1.00

Model fittings

We fitted the SDMs with the dismo package in maxent (Hijmans *et al.* 2015), as described in the previous section. We used maxent as it is known to absorb variation from multiple

variables more efficiently than other fitting procedures, and we were interested on knowing whether the addition of other variables biased the response to aridity. For this analysis, we included the variables described above. We prevented the interaction terms in maxent to be able to obtain aridity niches when controlling for the rest of variables in a next step. The TSS of these models is displayed in Figure SA 1.2, and are reported with the data used in this study (Berdugo *et al.* 2018).

Validation of main results

We ran the analyses described in step ii of the manuscript calculating AAb with the niches obtained with several predictors. To do that, we set the values of predictors other than aridity to the mean value of the occurrences of each species. The resulting suitability curve is the aridity niche filtered by the rest of the predictors. We used interpolation of the species performance (niche adequacy) in these curves to extract new values of AAb. The results obtained were very similar to those reported in the original manuscript (see Figure SA 2.3).

Figure SA. 2.3. Results of the analysis described in step ii of the manuscript with Aab extracted from multi-varied niches. Standardized effect sizes of facilitation, competition and aridity-driven abundance (a) and the interactions between aridity-driven abundance and competition and facilitation (b) as drivers of species relative abundance along an aridity gradient. This analysis is performed by fitting a linear mixed models throughout a moving window in a subset of the sites surveyed following our aridity gradient. Bootstrapped coefficients of this regression with their 95% confidence intervals are shown for each step of the moving window. Lines represent the gam-smoothed trends of variation of the effect sizes.

APPENDIX S3: INCLUSION OF ADDITIONAL VARIABLES TO ASSESS THE RELATIVE COVER OF THE SPECIES

Rationale of selection of variables

Because the statistical models used in the main manuscript exhibited low R^2 values, the variables selected originally might be confounded by other variables that explain better community assembly processes. Although it is not the purpose of this study to assess all possible plant community assembly factors in drylands, we repeated the analyses using two additional variables that are known to be related both to community assembly and the importance of biotic interactions. These variables were: average phylogenetic distance of species and rarity.

Species that are closely related usually are more similar, and therefore its interactions are predominantly of competition (Cahill *et al.* 2008). Conversely, facilitation is found more frequently between species that are distantly related (Valiente-Banuet & Verdú 2007; Soliveres, Torices & Maestre 2012). At the same time, average phylogenetic distance is measuring an extra proportion of niche variability (similitude between species) that might not be entirely correlated with aridity niches. It has been shown that high variability of phylogenetic differences in communities correspond to sites in which biotic interactions tend to dominate the assembly rules (Helmus *et al.* 2007; Valiente-Banuet & Verdú 2007; Godoy, Kraft & Levine 2014) and, conversely, in those sites in which abiotic factors tend to filter strongly the community average phylogenetic distances are reduced (Helmus *et al.* 2007; Cavender-Bares *et al.* 2009). These patterns however, are currently under discussion (see (Mayfield & Levine 2010; Gerhold *et al.* 2015).

Species are locally rare either because they are poor competitors or because they show low reproductive performance (Beck *et al.* 2013b). Rarity of species influence the probability of occurrence of a target species because of obvious reasons. At the same time, some studies have found that facilitative interactions occur predominantly over rare species (Soliveres *et al.* 2015).

Assessing the new variables

We obtained phylogenetic distances between pairs of species from data of a previous work (see details in Appendix C of Soliveres *et al.* 2014). Briefly, we assembled the phylogenetic tree using the Phylocom 4.1 software (Webb, Ackerly & Kembel 2008), standard phylogenetic protocols and published phylogenies. We calculated phylogenetic distances between species using the *cophenetic* function in R, which is assembled in package *picante* (Kembel *et al.* 2010). We weighted the phylogenetic distance between target species and the others by the relative abundance of the others, thus obtaining a metric informing about the weighted distance of each target species with their companions.

To obtain rarity, we used the total number of occurrence data of GBIF. We assumed that the more rare the species, the more infrequent they would be found in GBIF. It is worth to note that this metric of rarity at these scales would be probably more related with low reproductive rates than with suboptimal local rarity (see Williams *et al.* 2009).

Both phylogenetic distances and occurrence data were log-transformed and added in the model described in step iii of the main text. Because this analysis reduced the total number of cases up to 631, we were not able to perform moving windows and thus we tested the overall model including the interactions with aridity of the original variables, which is equivalent. The results are displayed in Figure SA. 3.1.

Figure SA. 3.1. Results of the main analyses of the paper described in step iii, including average phylogenetic distances and rarity. Violin diagram showing the bootstrapped standardized effects of aridity, aridity-driven abundance (Aab), Facilitation (Fab), Competition (Cab), Height (Hgt), Rarity, average phylogenetic distance (AvgPD), the interactions between the Fab and Cab with Rarity and avgPD, and the interactions of Fab, Cab and Aab with Aridity to drive the local relative abundance of species. The violin plot is similar to a box plot but it features a kernel density estimation of the underlying distribution per parameter and displays it as the width of the form. Marginal and conditional R^2 are displayed in the upper right part of the graph.

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